

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

NEUROTECHNOLOGY, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE & BLOCKCHAIN FOR EDUCATION

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Abstract

The connection of artificial intelligence with neurotechnology is considered. The problem of scientific validity of transferring the results of studies of the synaptic level of brain activity to the personal; the ethical problem of invasion of personal space; the social and legal problem of storing confidential information are posed and discussed.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, neurotechnology, blockchain, education.

Artificial Intelligence is a very broad field of computer science in which computers model the neuroprocesses of thinking, learning, and perception. The term "artificial intelligence" has been used since 1956, but only in recent years has there been a significant shift in it, with the emergence of Deep Learning, machine learning, that is, machine learning.

Artificial intelligence is already part of the digitalization of our lives. It helps us quickly find the information we need using a search engine, make almost instant translations into other languages, and perform complex calculations.

Neuroscientists (neurobiology, neurophysiology, neurogenetics) are the source of knowledge about the brain. They use different technologies for their discoveries, and first of all, neurotechnologies. Neurotechnologies are tools for studying the brain, consciousness, thinking activity, higher mental functions, in order to treat and rehabilitate patients with neurological problems. Neurotechnologies allow researchers to visualize the brain, to observe how it works right during experiments. For example, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) makes it possible to build a map of associative connections between different areas and regions of the brain and identify new functional areas and regions. Patients can see in real time how their brain responds to stimuli, thereby receiving visual feedback. The use of functional magnetic resonance imaging has changed the way we look at autonomic patients (coma or minimally conscious patients). As it turned out, they can retain emotions, understand words and even be aware of what is going on around them. This raises the problem of the legitimacy of relatives of patients with severe brain injuries to decide about their life or death. After all, it is not uncommon for such patients, who have been in a vegetative state for a long time, to suddenly recover.

Transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) affects the brain with magnetic impulses, affecting the electrical activity of the brain. Positron emission tomography (PET) is an imaging technique that detects brain metabolic processes: thus, problem areas of the brain consume increased amounts of glucose and become "visible" on the screen.

Computed tomography (CT) is a technology for detecting brain activity and damage (injury/disease

such as aneurysms or cancer). Despite their differences, all of these technologies solve primarily medical problems and help improve brain mapping, but they are incredibly far from the practice of education. They have helped develop drugs for depression, insomnia, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, anti-neurotic drugs, drugs for stroke recovery, reducing the frequency of epilepsy attacks, and relief of phantom pain [2].

However, experts believe that today brain scans are often seen as more accurate and objective than they really are. While neuroimaging technologies are extremely important for diagnosis, the interpretation of brain activity patterns as applied to healthy people can hardly be called perfect.

Nevertheless, the idea of using neurotechnology not on a damaged brain, but on a healthy one, not individually, but massively, in order to optimize brain activity is not only alive, but it is becoming more and more detailed, including scandalous ones. For example, such a form of neurostimulation as microstimulation is being investigated. It uses low-voltage direct current, which is delivered directly to the area of interest in the brain through small electrodes. While previously this technique was used to help patients with brain damage (such as strokes), today experiments are also being conducted on healthy people. Although the results are contradictory, there is already evidence that the technique affects the cognitive abilities of the brain depending on the area it is stimulated (we are talking about language, mathematical abilities, attention, memory, coordination). Not only the ethical side of the use of such technologies is debatable, but also the question of the safety of the object of influence, the interference in privacy and individual psychological space [3,4].

This is also the problem of the use of neuroimplants - the insertion of devices into the cranial cavity that are used to control or regulate brain activity. Their purpose is to improve any parameters of body functioning by deep stimulation of the brain. Implants help with Parkinson's disease, chronic pain, and clinical depression when regular pills don't work. But implants can also affect neighboring areas of the brain, changing a person's perception and behavior. If this leads to negative consequences, who is legally and morally responsible for them? Would it be the patient, the doctor, or the manufacturer of the implant? If the use of implants

for clinical applications (such as Parkinson's disease) is not in doubt, then the possibility of "chipping" a healthy person's brain to control their behavior is now a reality and a major threat to the human rights to freedom and safety [5].

There are also many unresolved issues in the use of neuroimaging data in the criminal justice system, in identifying the connection between brain activity and deliberate deception. It is no coincidence that neurotechnology is an area of focus for intelligence services, from lie detectors to understanding the psyche, reducing "fear" and overcoming post-traumatic stress syndrome. Virtual reality technologies attract the attention of the military. Research in transcranial direct current stimulation, aimed at expanding soldiers' capabilities, is of great interest to the U.S. military.

The progress of neuroscience is unstoppable. The more substantial their results are, the more tempting new areas of their application become. Neuroethics cannot keep up not only with the progress of science and technology, but also with the emergence of more and more types of speculation, deception, manipulation of our consciousness. This situation calls for a deeper study of the ethical implications of introducing the results of scientific research that affect health and safety. Any ethical approach must be based on respect for the individual and for privacy.

However, the possibility of applying the spatial pattern to the theory of education is critical [1]. In addition to the benefits, neuroscience has a flip side, the comprehension of which requires addressing the problem of subjectivity of participants in the inclusive educational process. The results of neuroscience research have different forms: physical (electrical), chemical, spatial, temporal, and pedagogy refers to the behavior of the subject, his relationship to himself and the world, to culture. Education is a form of transmitting culture to a new generation. The neuroimaging methodology used in neurotechnology in its present form is unsuitable for solving pedagogical socio-psychological problems, issues of subjectivity and subject relations of participants of educational process [5,6]. It is obviously premature to declare the emergence of neuropedagogy and neuroeducation only based on the development of neurotechnology means

Many complex issues related to the interaction between the brain and "artificial intelligence" remain unresolved

In addition, there is evidence of the destructive effects of neurotechnology in the unformed digital culture of its participants (neuroculture). Subjectivity is eliminated, put "outside" as a rudiment of "outmoded" human nature. "Transhuman" goals, embedded in neuro-education already at the stage of technology and device design, can destroy a person's normal relationship with himself and the world, block his formation and improvement as a subject.

Since neurotechnologies imply direct intervention into human consciousness, they change human identity, up to the point of forming a "transhuman". Therefore,

the transformations taking place should be studied in the context of changes in human attitudes toward himself and the surrounding world, as well as the evolution of the values and goals, concepts and notions, patterns of behavior and interaction regulating these attitudes. Obviously, without a dialogue between a person and a person (a learner and a mentor, a teacher) no education and training, even "amplified" by digital and neurotechnologies, is possible

The problems of information privacy when using artificial intelligence lead to a discussion of the prospects of combining it with blockchain technology. The use of this technology is often hampered by the fact that it is associated only with cryptocurrency, which is wrong. Blockchain is a big data technology that allows to store information laid down by different people in an unchanged form with an absolute guarantee of confidentiality. Today, this technology is rapidly being implemented in different spheres of life, including education. It can be a portfolio of a person's achievements, his authentic documents, including diplomas of education, an indication of the teachers the person studied with, their qualifications, the names of the courses, the technologies used, including the digitalization of education.

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